

THE PRIORITY TASKS OF THE STATE POLICY IN EFL EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This article is about learning foreign languages, thinking that foreign languages are not only a means of communication, but also a door to many opportunities, and the importance of learning foreign languages in human life.

Key words: foreign languages, effective methods, means of communication, new approach to teaching

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Today knowing foreign languages means keeping up with the times. A person who knows foreign languages has more opportunities than other people to learn and know the customs and culture of other countries, and his mind is wide and his memory is much better developed. Today knowledge of foreign languages is one of the necessary conditions of professional competence, which gives the specialist an edge in the labor market. Qualified knowledge in various areas of human life be it scientific theories or business information, in many cases can only be obtained from foreign sources. At follows that the professional level directly depends on having modern information and, in turn, on the level of knowledge of a foreign language.

The 21st century has brought radical changes to Uzbekistan that effect all areas of the social system, and this cannot fail to effect the political, social economic and cultural levels. The administrative economic system was replaced by market relations, which in turn leads to social changes of citizens. Modern youth felt the independence and personal responsibility of each of them for their future and the future of their country. Along with freedom, it is time to realize the need to take initiative, use knowledge and accumulated experience, take responsibility for decisions made, and achieve set goals. These factors mean that modernity has a high level of professionalism. The dialectic of globalization implies the formation of a mixed world culture, the foundation of the state, the interconnection and strengthening of relations between people. Great advances in telecommunications, great advances in computer technology, and the emergence of social networks such as the Internet are powerful catalysts for globalization. As a result the interdependence of countries with each other is increasing. National cultures rate and often merge to form indivisible integrated structures. This leads to an increase in migration to the flow of capital to the formation of communication and transportation networks that cover our planet. Globalization, capital flow, technological progress, spiritual achievement help to overcome the obstacles to acquiring new knowledge and providing qualified

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services. The main condition for the development and independence of any country, including Uzbekistan, is to join the world space, Uzbekistan is slowly but surely going its own way. Nowadays, improving the quality of education, improving skills and qualifications for learning foreign languages has become one of the priority tasks of the state policy in the field of education. More stimulation of scientific activities focused on new approach to teaching foreign languages, in this important to focus on the practical effectiveness of scientific work. The development and introduction of a practical testing of the methods developed by scientific researches directly in educational institutions will undoubtedly lead to effective results. It is important to pay attention to the quality of education from the primary school in order to be able to speak a foreign language fluently and freely. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that a child who learned a trade and learned a language from school is a great achievement of our society. The pedagogues of higher educational institutions were given the task of in-depth study and teaching of foreign languages, using the advanced and innovative pedagogical experiences of developed countries, and on this basic, creating modern and effective methods of teaching foreign languages. The task of introducing modern communicative competence methods in teaching foreign languages and evaluating the knowledge of young students is also becoming an important task on the agenda. Requirements and professors pay special attention to the level of knowledge of foreign languages, international and national qualification certificates, including IELTS, CEFR, APTIS, TKT, CELTA, TESOL and professors and students with this certificate are encouraged. Today, our universities have established cooperative relations with many foreign countries. Cooperation agreements have been signed with Norwich University of Great Britain, Post University, Several universities of France and Turkey, Moscow State Pedagogical University of the Russian Federation, Tula State Pedagogical Universities of the Republic of Kazakhstan and many other higher education. The time has come to establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on school, lyceum, college and university graduates must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that this strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution. Thus, it can be concluded that language is the engine and component of all spheres of society's life. Language is an important factor in the implementation cooperation and plays a major role in deciding the communicative direction. One of the important factors of implementation is the educational factor. Language competences are of great importance in the formation of a mixed world culture, in connecting the foundations of the mutual relations between peoples. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the dynamics of the globalization process. Language develops the ability to think creativity, analyze and understand the surrounding situation. Foreign language enables young personnel to compete in the world labor market.

Har tilni biluvemdiadomajondir

Til vositai robitai alamiyondir

G'ayritilni say qiling, bilgali yoshlar

Kim ilm-u hunarlar rivoji ondin ayondir.

In conclusion, language skills are important and key to new opportunities for every industry representative. One door to professionals who know this profession. Another door opens for language specialists. Knowing a language is the key to unlocking the door of the whole world.

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